

SYSTEMATIC DESCRIPTION OF THE ALLOCHRUSA GYPSOPHILOIDES REGEL PLANT

Annotation: *Allochrusa gypsophiloides regel* is a perennial herb belonging to the Caryophyllaceae family. Stem strongly branched, short hairy or glabrous. As a result of the repeated branching of the stems, the plant has a spherical shape, and its height reaches 70-80 cm with almost the same diameter.

Keywords: *Allochrusa gypsophiloides regel*, plant, flower, method, region.

INTRODUCTION

Leaves are opposite, up to 3 cm long and 0.5 cm wide, flat, almost linear or linear-lanceolate, pointed at the tip. Bracts opposite, subulate, glabrous, 2-3 times shorter than calyx. The flowers are loose, forked-twigs, in broad paniced inflorescences at the top of stems and branches. The middle flower in each spike of the inflorescence is almost persistent, the other 2 are on long filiform pedicels. Calyx five-lobed, cylindrical, glabrous, about 2 mm long; corolla with 5 pink petals, one-celled ovary, 10 stamens. The seeds are light brown, almost spherical, slightly flattened on the sides, ripen in early August, but do not disintegrate until autumn. The root is rhizome-like, sometimes fusiform, twisted, up to 2 m long and more, weighing up to 12 kg. Several branched lateral roots emerge from the tap root. Thorny thorn (Turkistan soap root) does not have the ability to regenerate after its roots are dug up, so the natural thickets of this plant do not regenerate after harvesting.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Etmak (Allochrusa gypsophiloides regel) is found only in the mountains of Central Asia from the foothills to the middle mountain belt. It is found in the Hisar range in the south. The eastern border passes through the Western Tien Shan, and the western border passes through the mountains of Turkmenistan. Coniferous trees mainly belong to the belt of ephemeral plants, deep-rooted long-growing perennials and semi-shrubs, and lower among meadow-steppe and tree-shrub vegetation. there are mountain and mid-mountain zones. As a result of the plowing of the land and mass collection of the roots of this plant, the area of natural mountain ranges has decreased.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Its industrial branches in Uzbekistan: Tashkent region (Piskent, Middle Chirchik, Ohangaron, Upper Chirchik, Parkent and Bostanliq districts), Fergana Valley (Kassonsoy, Tora-Kurgan, Chust, Papa and Namangan neighborhoods), Samarkand (Urgut, Pastdargom districts) and Jizzakh regions (Galla-Arol,

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Jizzakh, Karakishloq districts) - in the Sangzor river basin and adjacent areas, the hilly zone of the Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya river basins (Kokoulak, Boysun, Qamashi, Dehkanabad , around the villages of Yakkabog, Chirakchi, Kitab and Miraki), located in the mountains of Boysun District (Kugitangtau) of Surkhandarya Region. The content of saponins almost does not depend on the size of the roots. In short, from the day when the Republic of Uzbekistan was declared independent (August 31, 1991), fundamental changes were initiated in almost all areas of our country. For example, in Article 55 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is strictly stated that "Land, underground resources, water, flora and fauna and other natural resources are national wealth, they must be used wisely and they are under state protection." In this regard, a number of measures have been taken in our Republic to protect nature, including flora. As a continuation of these activities, the Nature Protection Committee was established in our Republic, and the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved the decision on the protection and use of flora on December 26, 1997.

This plant is mainly distributed in Jizzakh region. The territory of the province is diverse in terms of geological structure, it consists of mountain ranges that were formed during the formation of the Hertzian mountain. During the formation of the Alps, the mountains in the south of the region rose again, and the parts of the plain that were under water until that time turned into dry land as a result of the uplift. In the geological structure of the Earth's surface, various Paleozoic deposits can be seen in Zomin, Chumkortog, Molguzar and Nurota mountains, Meso-Cenozoic deposits are involved in the structure of plains and mountainous areas. Paleozoic deposits are mainly found in sedimentary and metamorphic rocks, while Mesozoic deposits consist only of sedimentary rocks, and igneous rocks are relatively rare. Scientists A.P. Markovskiy, I. Hamroboev, Sh.A. Davlatov, O.A. Rajabov and others made a great contribution to the study of the geological structure of the region. The appearance of the current surface of the region was influenced by complex changing geological conditions, and it is distinguished by its uniqueness in different regions. Even today, the surface of the earth is changing. We can give an example of the impact of human economic activity. As a result of this effect, a new anthropogenic form of relief is emerging. The structure of the region's surface is uneven, and it can be seen that plains, hills, foothills and mountains are interwoven. According to experts, orographically, Jizzakh region is divided into two sharply different parts - plains and mountains. The northern part of the region consists mainly of plains and lowlands, and on the other sides it is surrounded by Chumkortog, Molguzar and Nurota mountains, which are branches of the Turkestan range. These two parts have certain differences according to the topography and geological structure. For example, the plain part of the region slopes to the northwest, and the average height is 250-300 meters.

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CONCLUSION

Harvesting of roots should be done in a short time and start in the second half of April. The optimal time for harvesting is the second half of May - the beginning of June. The excavated roots are first cleaned, the remains of the stem are cut and dried in the sun. In rainy weather, drying is done under awnings. It is not necessary to cut the roots into pieces before drying. Artificial drying is also possible (at a temperature of heating the roots up to 40-50 ° C).

REFERENCES

1. Integration of science, education and production in the development of modern biological education. April 8, 2022.
2. Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute Norkulova Munura (article) Tashkent 2021
3. Botany, study guide. A. Matkarimova, T. Makhkamov, M. Makhmudova, Khamidjon Azizov, G. Vaisova Tashkent "Teacher" 2018 p. 353
4. Рашидов Диловар Нажмиддинович, & Холбоев Йигитали Авганович (2022). КОРХОНА ВА ТАШКИЛОТЛАРДА ИЖТИМОЙИ ҲИМОЯГА МУҲТОЖ ШАХСЛАР УЧУН ИШ ҶРИНЛАРИНИ ЙЎНАЛИШЛАР КЕСИМИДА ЗАХИРАЛАШНИНГ САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШ. Трансформация моделей корпоративного управления в условиях цифровой экономики, 1 (1), 73-78. doi: 10.24412/cl-36899-2022-1-73-78
5. From the website <https://ziyonet.uz/>.

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